

Portal empowers prize-winning concept

Portal Admin

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[SCIENCE NEWS]

This community-powered portal has for years nurtured various environment-friendly research concepts and approaches, with one of its early views being the principle for building an “eco-surplus culture” [1].

On August 16, 2024, two co-founders of the portal, Vuong Quan Hoang and Nguyen Minh Hoang, were awarded the “Ngon Lua” (Blaze) Journalism Prize for their contribution to the development of this very principle. The prize, which was awarded for the seventh (VII) time this year, is organized by the 94-year-old [Communist Review](#), the most important theoretical politics publication in Vietnam.

Photo: Portal's contributors receiving the prize (second and third from the left) ©2024
Courtesy of Duc Tuan ([People's Army Daily](#), Aug. 16)

In the course of scientific pursuits, the platform has continually supported further advances in this direction, leading new views concerning a critically important element, but usually taken for granted: the notion of value [2-3]. These advances are expected to empower deeper considerations of theoretical developments concerning social sciences and humanities theory-making.

***Remarks:** The event was covered by numerous leading newspapers, such as [People's Army](#), [People Daily](#), [New Hanoi](#), and many others.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2021). The semiconducting principle of monetary and environmental values exchange. *Economics and Business Letters*, **10**(3), 284-290. <https://doi.org/10.17811/ebl.10.3.2021.284-290>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. <https://books.google.com/books?id=I50TEQAAQBAJ>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOARN>

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